

A STUDY ON THE PROBLEMS FACED BY THE TEA PLANTATION WORKERS IN THE NILGIRIS DISTRICT, TAMILNADU

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ABSTRACT

This study explores the challenges faced by tea plantation workers in the Nilgiris District, Tamil Nadu, focusing on their socio-economic conditions, working environments, and overall satisfaction. The Nilgiris District, a key tea-growing region, has experienced significant changes impacting its workforce, despite its appeal as a tourist destination. Economic hardships, natural hazards, and labor practices contribute to the difficulties encountered by these workers. Using a descriptive research design and simple random sampling, the study collected data from tea factory employees in three taluks: Ooty, Gudalur, and Coonoor. The research involved primary data gathered through structured interviews with 600 workers and secondary data from industry reports and academic sources. The analysis aimed to uncover issues such as exploitation, gender discrimination, career development opportunities, and the effects of financial support on workers' livelihoods. The findings highlight significant problems, including poor working conditions, limited career advancement, and gender-based disparities. The study also assesses the impact of financial interventions and levels of worker satisfaction. The results offer valuable insights into improving conditions and well-being for tea plantation workers in the Nilgiris District, with recommendations for policy reforms and enhanced labor practices.

Keywords: Tea plantation workers, Nilgiris District, socio-economic conditions, working environments, labor practices, gender discrimination, career development, financial support, worker satisfaction, statistical analysis.

INTRODUCTION

India's exports include a sizable portion of tea estates, which are produced across the nation. Along with Southern states like Tamil Nadu, Kerala, and Karnataka, the North Eastern States are particularly well-known for their tea plantations and production. India produced over 1991.76 million kilograms of tea in 2020, a significant rise from 853.7 million kilograms in 2001 and evidence of the industry's significant expansion. Nationwide, the total area planted with tea increased from 509,806 hectares in 2001 to 578,000 hectares in 2020. About 178,000 hectares of tea are grown in South India, which includes Tamil Nadu, Kerala, Karnataka, and Andhra Pradesh. Of these, 95,000 hectares are in the Nilgiris area alone. This region produces roughly 32 million kilograms of tea annually. In Tamil Nadu, the districts of Kodaikanal, Nilgiris, Valparai, and

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Manjolai in Tirunelveli are among those where tea is grown. In Tamil Nadu, the Nilgiris district is very important for tea plantations.

During their reign, the British government started initiatives for tea plantations, hiring refugees, migrants, repatriates, indigenous tribes, and other local groups to help grow the industry into a significant one. It is usual to find tribal laborers from groups like the Kurumbas and Irulas working on the Kotagiri region's tea estates. Tribes like the Paniyas and Kattunaickens work on tea plantations in the Gudalur and Pandalur districts.

At present, there are around 17 INDCO (Industrial Co-operative Tea Factories) and around 12 familiar trade unions for tea laborers have been functioning in the district. It became evident during the field study that the tribal tea laborers' precarious situation was due to their complete economic and social regression from the present generations. They are ignorant of labor laws; in fact, they do not even know what "labour law" is. The majority of tea labourers from ethnic backgrounds were not members of any trade unions. This is also one of the reasons for being crushed by the tea companies which were run by private bodies.

They were not able to mention their actual working timings. It differs from day to day. But they worked for more hours which was against the laborer working time advised by the labour laws. Their previous generation might have been involved in some traditional occupation of the tribes, but due to economic reasons and sometimes by the influence of neighboring tea factories, they were forced to be employed as tea laborers. It was not evident that the companies were providing proper safety measures for tea laborers. Moreover, the tribal tea laborer faces more difficulties in their work environment. Major tea estates are at the border of thick forests. So the management of those companies prefers nearby residing repatriates and the tribes as the labourers.

The repatriates and the tribal tea labourers face problems like insect bites, snake bites, animal attacks, etc. Apart from these, they also suffer waterborne diseases which are common due to the humidity in those areas. Consistent deaths occur due to such factors.

Education is prohibited directly or indirectly by some of the estate management. They wanted their laborers to bring their children also to the estates to assist them or some other tasks would be given to those children. Repatriates Labourers and Tribal tea labourers hesitate to move towards urban regions which they consider as insecurity. Many tribal tea laborer do not have their land for agriculture.

These are some of the reasons for Repatriates and tribal tea labourers to enroll themselves in the nearby tea factories. There are six taluks in the Nilgiris district namely Udthagamandalam, Coonoor, Kotagiri, Gudalur, Kundah, and Pandalur, and 18 urban units. The total population of the district is 735,394. 75% of them are resettled (Repartitioned People) tea workers and tribals. The Repatriates and tribal groups which have been concentrated for the study include Kurumbas, Irulas, Todas, Kattu Naickans, Kotas, and Paniyas. Kotagiri, Coonoor, and Gudalur Taluks are the study areas taken into consideration.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Tea cultivation is a major source of income for many people in the Nilgiris District, where a significant proportion of the workforce in tea factories consists of tribal individuals. The tea plantation sector plays a crucial role in providing livelihoods for a large segment of the district's population. The Nilgiris District in Tamil Nadu accounts for 14% of South India's total tea production and approximately 3% of India's overall tea production. Tea produced in Tamil Nadu is largely geared towards the export market, while tea from North India primarily meets domestic demand.

This study aims to investigate whether tea factories exploit local employees and to assess the presence of gender discrimination within the tea factories of the Nilgiris District. It seeks to evaluate the benefits and prospects employees gain from working in tea factories, including the impact of bank loans on their socio-economic status, and to measure employee satisfaction across different job roles within the factories. Additionally, the study will identify problems faced by employees that significantly affect their lifestyles and address these issues based on the analysis results. The objectives of the study are framed to address these key issues and provide insights for improvement.

SCOPE OF THE STUDY

This study investigates the challenges faced by tea plantation workers in the Nilgiris District, Tamil Nadu. It explores the economic impact of tea cultivation on workers, including their income and living standards, and examines working conditions such as health and safety. The research assesses whether workers are exploited due to their proximity to factories and if gender discrimination exists. It also evaluates career development opportunities, the impact of financial support from institutions, and overall employee satisfaction. Additionally, the study identifies key issues affecting workers' lives, such as health, living conditions, and access to services, aiming to provide insights for improving their well-being.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To ascertain the Socioeconomic profile of the Repatriates and Tribal tea labourers.
- To Examine the problems faced by the Repatriates and tribal tea labourers.
- To find out the factory impact contributing to problems and bank intervention leading to prospects of the employees of Tea Factory.
- To understand the level of satisfaction achieved through direct and mediated effects.
- To contribute suggestions for management policy implication to overcome the difficult situation existing in the Tea Factory.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

- **Area of the Study:**
 - The Nilgiris District, renowned for its picturesque hill stations and significant tourist influx, has experienced substantial changes over time. These changes, coupled with the impact of natural hazards, have affected the economic well-being of the local population, highlighting the need to address the issues faced by tea factory workers in this region.
- **Research Design:**
 - The study employs a descriptive research design to provide a comprehensive analysis of the problems and prospects faced by tea plantation workers in the Nilgiris District.
- **Sampling Procedure:**
 - A simple random sampling procedure was utilized to ensure representative and authoritative results. The study focused on tea manufacturing companies within the Nilgiris District, selecting ten companies from three key taluks: Ooty, Gudalur, and Coonoor.

DATA SOURCES:

- **Primary Data:** Data was collected through a structured interview schedule administered to employees working in various roles across selected tea factories. The survey included 842 employees, with 783 responses initially gathered. After eliminating 183 incomplete or inconsistent responses, 600 valid samples were analyzed.
- **Secondary Data:** Secondary data sources include publications and reports from the Tea Board of India, the United Planters Association of Southern India (UPASI), the State Planning Board of Tamil Nadu, tea companies' reports, unpublished research reports, doctoral theses, books, research articles from refereed journals, and news articles from 'Tea Statistics' and 'Tea Digest.'

PILOT STUDY:

A pilot study involving 60 participants was conducted to pre-test the interview schedule. Based on the results, the schedule was refined to enhance clarity and effectiveness, leading to the development of a conceptual model and study design.

SAMPLING DESIGN AND UNIT OF ANALYSIS:

The study used simple random sampling to select tea manufacturing companies in the Nilgiris District. Three taluks (Ooty, Gudalur, and Coonoor) were chosen for data collection. Respondents were given adequate time to complete the questionnaire. The final dataset included responses from 600 participants (200 from each taluk) after excluding 183 incomplete or erroneous responses.

Total Number of Questionnaires					
Circulated	Returned	Not Returned	Incomplete	Extreme Response	Final Sample
783	750	33	60	90	600

FRAMEWORK OF ANALYSIS

The primary goal of the study is to explore the issues and opportunities that impact employee satisfaction in selected tea manufacturing companies in the Nilgiris District, Tamil Nadu. The data collected for this research were quantified, categorized, and organized using various statistical methods to achieve the study's objectives. Analytical tools employed include Percentage Analysis, Weighted Average, Garrett Ranking Method, Mean Score Analysis, One-way ANOVA, Chi-Square Test, Correlation Analysis, Regression Analysis, Factor Analysis, and Structural Equation Modeling.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

- The survey has been conducted only within the District of the Nilgiris.
- The survey is based on convenient sampling as the Repatriate and tribal settlements are hard to reach via roads.
- The data are collected from 1200 respondents and the findings may not be universally applicable.

FINDINGS

- It is clear that more than half of the respondents have 4 to 5 members in their family, the majority of the respondents live in their own houses, while, more than half of the respondents have only one earning member in their family and finally, it is found that 40.7% of the respondents have got the job through various means (like contractor, advertisement, etc.)

- It is observed that there is a low positive correlation between communal reasons and constructive reasons and, a moderate positive correlation between constructive reasons and financial reasons.
- From the regression results, it is concluded that the association between the two factors was high based on the financial reasons for joining the tea factory and had highly influenced the worker's empowerment. Therefore it is clear that the hypothesis results were found to be partially significant to reject the null hypothesis.
- It is evident from the above table that all the respondents had agreed that they were able to get a bank loan after joining the tea factory.
- It is understood that the majority (83.3%) of the respondents used bank loans for their purposes.

SUGGESTIONS

- It is understood that the household consumables are found to have adequately improved and helped to enhance the employees living conditions, however, there are a few respondents who have not got everything available in their family needed to be observed closely by the Tea Factory Human Resource department by having a direct interaction with the workers and spotting their needs to lead a life adequately filled with household necessities.
- Even, the bank loans are obtained by all the employees it is observed that very few employees voiced dissatisfaction with the utilization of loans and improvement in their lives. It is recommended that to perk up the worker's advancement by closely observing their commitment and requirement by the management and educate them to utilize their bank loan which they felt not adequate concerning children's education, clearing old debts, insufficient loan amount to meet family commitment and lack of improvement in agricultural activities and also medical facilities.

CONCLUSION

The study's findings are based on the opinions of tea factory workers, who shared their thoughts on a few issues that the management has failed to solve. The majority of workers in the tea factories expressed optimism and saw improvements in their personal lives, and they also felt empowered as a result of the bank's intervention in providing sufficient loan amounts to the right candidates to improve their social and economic standing. These actions significantly raised the level of satisfaction among the workforce. The statistical findings, however, indicate that there are a few issues that the management has to address to improve the prospects for their workers' lifestyles. If these ideas are taken into consideration, the Tea Factories will be able to reach even higher heights in the years to come.

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